

UltraGCN: Ultra Simplification of Graph Convolutional Networks for Recommendation

Exercise 2: Reproduce experimental results from a paper

Experiment Design for Data Science – WS 2023/24 – Group 15-A

Behaein Arash, B.A., Behaein

Vienna University of Technology, Informatics, e12324255@student.tuwien.ac.at

Isufi Amareldo, I.R., Isufi

Vienna University of Technology, Informatics, e52003907@student.tuwien.ac.at

Stani Mario, S.M., Stani

Vienna University of Technology, Informatics, e52003945@student.tuwien.ac.at

Šantek Luka, Š.L., Šantek

Vienna University of Technology, e12332270@student.tuwien.ac.at

1 INTRODUCTION

Objective of this paper is reproduction of experimental results from the paper [1] and result comparison with values given in the paper. Goal is to evaluate performance and efficiency of newly proposed UltraGCN algorithm, as well as explore how different parameter settings effect the performance. Conclusions about reproductivity of the experiment will be made.

2 PERFORMANCE AND EFFICIENCY ANALYSIS

To conduct performance and efficiency analysis of UltraGCN algorithm, we have run the experiment for 4 different datasets, as suggested in the original paper [1] Amazon-Book, Yelp2018, Gowalla, and MovieLens-1M. For all the datasets, except for Amazon-Book, experiment was successfully reproduced following instructions given in the original paper. Failure to reproduce the experiment for dataset Amazon-Book is caused by insufficient RAM memory (DefaultCPUAllocator error occurred while running the experiment). To run the experiment for this dataset successfully, special hardware would be needed.

2.1 Experimental setup

Environment to run the code was created step by step completely based on the instructions from the paper. No difficulties were encountered, since all the required code and datasets were provided as part of GitHub repository (<https://reczoo.github.io/UltraGCN>) and all the instructions were available. Experimental setup for different datasets slightly differs, since different computer systems were used for running the experiment, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Experimental setup for performance and efficiency analysis

DATASET	MOVIELENS-1M, YELP2018	GOWALLA, AMAZON-BOOK
PROCESSOR	Intel Core i7-7500U 2.70 GHz	Intel Core i5 2GHz
RAM	12 GB	16 GB
GPU	NVIDIA GeForce 940MX	Intel Iris Plus Graphics
PYTHON	3.7.6	3.10.4
PYTHON LIBRARIES	torch: 1.10.2+cu102	torch: 2.1.2
	NumPy: 1.19.5	NumPy: 1.22.1
	SciPy: 1.5.2	SciPy: 1.7.3
	tensorboard: 2.11.2	tensorboard: 2.15.1

2.2 Results and statistical comparison

Both results obtained by running the experiment and results given in the original paper [1] are shown in Table 2, as well as statistical difference between those values.

Table 2: Result comparison for different datasets

DATASET		YELP 2018	MOVIELENS-1M	GOWALLA
EARLY STOP ON EPOCH	PAPER	75	136	784
	EXPERIMENT	73	136	778
	DIFFERENCE	2	0	6
BEST EPOCH	PAPER	60	86	634
	EXPERIMENT	58	86	628
	DIFFERENCE	2	0	6
BEST RECALL @20	PAPER	0.068109	0.278617	0.186364
	EXPERIMENT	0.067716	0.277508	0.184967
	DIFFERENCE	0.000393	0.001109	0.001397
BEST NDCG @20	PAPER	0.055815	0.264211	0.158097
	EXPERIMENT	0.055608	0.263677	0.157143
	DIFFERENCE	0.000207	0.000534	0.000954

Conclusion: there is no significant statistical difference between results obtained by running the experiment and values given in the original paper [1].

Additionally, in Table 3, information about training time for each epoch and total time needed to reach convergence for each dataset needed while reproducing the experiment is shown.

Table 3: Training time for different dataset

DATASET	YELP 2018	MOVIELENS-1M	GOWALLA
TRAINING TIME / EPOCH	12-13 minutes	3-6 minutes	11-15 minutes
TOTAL TRAINING TIME TO REACH CONVERGENCE	16 hours, 5 minutes	9 hours, 50 minutes	7 days, 14 hours, 50 minutes

Conclusion: both training time and time needed to reach convergence are significant, which was not the cause in original findings. Reason for this is using commercial hardware and software. Precise time needed to reach convergence and

specific hardware and software being used in original paper to conduct the experiment were not mentioned, so calculating statistical differences is not possible.

3 PARAMETER ANALYSIS

In the research, the aim was to recreate the UltraGCN model precisely as outlined in the paper. However, due to limited resources, the focus was directed towards replicating the model using the Yelp dataset. The choice of this dataset stemmed from its practical suitability within the available resources and its crucial role in evaluating the reproducibility of the UltraGCN model.

3.1 Successful reproduction and consistent results

The subsequent reproduction of the UltraGCN model on the Yelp dataset yielded a commendable degree of success, with outcomes closely aligning with the original paper's findings. The observed consistency in performance metrics and outcomes implies the model's robustness and reproducibility, even under resource constraints. These results, graphically depicted in Figures 1 and 2, not only corroborate the original findings but also underscore the model's reliability across diverse executions and environments.

3.2 Comparison of Yelp results with paper's findings

A thorough examination of the results in comparison with the findings presented in the paper demonstrates striking similarities. Evaluation metrics, including Recall@20 and NDCG@20, showcase an almost identical pattern, offering compelling evidence of the model's consistent and effective performance. These results are visually depicted in Figure 1, illustrating the impact of altering the number of selected neighbors (K), and in Figure 2, elucidating the influence of constraint loss weights (λ and γ).

Figure 1: Performance comparison of setting different K

Figure 2: Performance comparison with different λ and γ .

3.3 Considerations

This acknowledged limitation emphasizes the necessity for future investigations to explore the reproducibility of the UltraGCN model across diverse datasets, contingent upon the availability of adequate resources. The successful reproduction of the UltraGCN model on the Yelp dataset substantiates its inherent robustness. Limitations encountered, particularly in relation to the unavailability of resources for the Amazon dataset, underscore the critical importance of scalability and resource considerations in scientific research. Future efforts could be aimed at broadening the range of datasets used for reproduction, enhancing the understanding of UltraGCN's applicability across diverse domains.

4 ABLATION STUDY

To identify key factors that significantly influence the outcomes of the UltraGCN model, the paper performs various experiments, by removing some of the hyperparameters systematically.

4.1 Reproduction difficulties

The paper mentions that these experiments were done solely on the *Amazon-Book* dataset. However, after various attempts, it was difficult to reproduce the results. This was mainly due to the size of the dataset and the lack of our computing resources. To work around this difficulty, we tried upgrading the resources to our capabilities and slightly modify the algorithms so that the data is processed in batches, but the system would still run out of memory. As a result, we decided not to compare our numbers directly with those on the paper, but to use the *Yelp* dataset for these experiments and see if the conclusions drawn in the paper can also be drawn from ours.

Although not crucial to the experiment, the code repository from the authors does not include code on how the plots itself were generated. However, since it is just an accuracy metric for various runs of the code, recreating the plots didn't pose a great difficulty.

4.2 Comparison of results

The results on the *Yelp* dataset show the same characteristics as those shown in the paper with the *Amazon-Books* one. In the paper, the importance of the parameters " γ " and " λ " is measured by removing them systematically and comparing the performance of the model. The paper shows that on the *Amazon-Books* dataset the default UltraGCN model performs the best. This was the case also in our experiments done with the *Yelp* dataset. The detailed results in comparison with those of the paper are shown in Figure 3. It should be noted that in the paper, the scales on the plot are adjusted so that they highlight the differences better.

Figure 3: Experiment with different “ γ ” and “ λ ” on *Yelp* (left) and on *Amazon-Books* (right)

Another study is done to show that augmenting positive user-item pairs for training to learn item-item relationships can achieve better performance than optimizing between item-item pairs. Again, this experiment was done on *Amazon-Books* by the paper and on *Yelp* by us. The results were also very similar and can be seen in more detail in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Performance comparison of using L'_i and L_i on *Yelp* (left) and on *Amazon-Books* (right)

4.3 Conclusions

The experiments concluded on the paper show proof that support the arguments raised by the authors on the ablation study. Although these experiments couldn’t be reproduced on the same dataset, their conclusions can be drawn also by the results on another dataset. This fortifies the credibility of the arguments, demonstrating their generalizability and reinforcing their merit.

REFERENCES

- [1] Kelong Mao, Jieming Zhu, Xi Xiao, Biao Lu, Zhaowei Wang, Xiuqiang He. 2021. UltraGCN: Ultra Simplification of Graph Convolutional Networks for Recommendation. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2110.15114>